

Full length article

Rise of amplified spontaneous emission in high-power thulium-doped fiber lasers and amplifiers due to self-heating

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Thulium-doped fiber laser
Amplified spontaneous emission
Self-heating
Thermal effects

ABSTRACT

The performance of high-power fiber lasers is limited by different thermal mechanisms such as a variation of spectroscopic quantities with temperature. In this paper, the effect of temperature dependent thulium cross sections on high-power thulium-doped fiber lasers and amplifiers pumped at 790 nm and operating above 1900 nm is investigated by means of numerical simulations and use of analytical models. The most significant self-heating effect was identified as an output signal power drop associated with increased amplified spontaneous emission caused by the temperature induced shift of the transparency wavelength of the single pass gain spectra.

1. Introduction

Among coherent light sources emitting in the 2- μm spectral range, thulium-doped fiber lasers (TDFL) play an important role [1–3], mainly thanks to a wide range of operation wavelengths reaching from 1700 up to 2200 nm [4–6]. High-power fiber lasers in general [7,8], including TDFLs, are known to be impaired by thermal effects due to heat generation in the doped region of an active fiber.

There are several temperature related factors affecting and limiting the performance and power scaling of TDFLs. The fiber can be physically destroyed by core melting [9] or by outer cladding/coating thermal damage [10] where the coating is usually the most vulnerable part of the fiber structure. Other adverse temperature-related effects include a transverse mode instability (TMI) [11], thermal fracture, lensing [12]. Furthermore, the effects caused by temperature dependence of spectroscopy parameters of rare-earth ions in silica could also influence the performance of TDFLs.

Thermal effects on fiber lasers including TDFLs have so far focused on different factors separately and also on their combination. For example, different heat dissipation management schemes including distributed pump were proposed [13], based on numerical analysis of kilowatt ytterbium-doped fiber lasers. The contribution of different heat sources to thermal distribution in an Yb-doped fiber was studied theoretically in [14]. An explanation of TMI in high-power fiber lasers was proposed in [15,16] and was studied on TDFLs both theoretically and experimentally, e.g. [17–19]. Temperature effects in

TDFLs were investigated by Huang et al. in [20] where the model based on the model [21] was assumed for thulium cross section temperature dependence. Resonantly pumped (at 1910 nm) Tm-doped amplifiers were thermally modeled in [22] where the power scaling limits were determined by comprehensive simulations taking into account all major thermal effects mentioned above, including thulium cross sections at pump and signal wavelengths. The performance of low power TDFLs operating in a heated environment was recently investigated in [23] using measured temperature dependent thulium cross section spectra [24].

Despite extensive research done so far, the question that remains almost non-tackled is how the temperature dependence of absorption and emission cross sections of Tm³⁺ ions in silica directly affects the performance of high-power TDFLs due to a *self-heating* process. The results in [20] are based on large extrapolations in temperature and are only partially relevant for high-power applications. Furthermore, the crucial modeling of amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) is carried out in an approximate way only in both [20,22]. Although the simulations presented in [23] contain fully resolved ASE spectra, their results are valid for low-power TDFLs in heated environments, but do not say much about self-heating in high-power lasers.

In this paper, the recently measured temperature dependent spectra of thulium cross sections [24,25] are utilized to analyze the self-heating effects on thulium-doped lasers and amplifiers. TDFL function is simulated by well established numerical and analytical models that

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Fig. 1. Energy level structure of Tm^{3+} ions in silica.

incorporate the measured cross section spectra. The analytical model is particularly congenial for its easy implementation, even with a simple spreadsheet editor, thus giving a quick physical insight of the effect of temperature dependent spectroscopic parameters to the laser threshold and slope efficiency. However, the analytical model does not account for important features of the fiber laser, namely the longitudinal dependence of the fiber-core temperature and the ASE. These effects will be studied by the comprehensive numerical model.

2. TDFL model

Numerical models varying in complexity were proposed and applied for TDFL simulation, e.g. [26–29]. They are based on a simultaneous numerical solution of laser rate and power propagation equations and provide reliable results in good agreement with experimental data. The general model presented below is based on these principles too.

2.1. Rate and propagation equations

The energy level structure of Tm^{3+} ions in silica is depicted in Fig. 1. Populations (i.e. concentrations of ions) at different energy levels vary according to the rate equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dN_1}{dt} = & N_0(W_{01} + W_{02}) - N_1(W_{10} + W_{13} + W_{14} + 1/\tau_1) \\ & + N_3(W_{31} + A_{31} + A_{32} + A_{33}^{\text{nr}}) + N_5(A_{51} + A_{52}) \\ & - 2k_{1130}N_1^2 + 2k_{3011}N_0N_3 - k_{1120}N_1^2 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dN_3}{dt} = & N_0W_{03} + N_1(W_{13} + W_{14}) \\ & - N_3(W_{35} + W_{31} + W_{30} + 1/\tau_3) \\ & + N_5(A_{53} + A_{54} + A_{55}^{\text{nr}}) \\ & + k_{1130}N_1^2 - k_{3011}N_0N_3 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dN_5}{dt} = N_0W_{05} + N_3W_{35} - N_5(W_{50} + 1/\tau_5) \quad (3)$$

$$0 = N_i - N_0 - N_1 - N_3 - N_5 \quad (4)$$

for populations (i.e. number of ions) at the i th level N_i [m^{-3}] where total lifetimes τ_i are related to radiative spontaneous emission rates A_{ij}

and non-radiative rates A_i^{nr} as:

$$\frac{1}{\tau_i} = A_i^{\text{nr}} + \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} A_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where $A_i^{\text{nr}} = 1/\tau_i^{\text{nr}}$. W_{ij} are stimulated absorption / emission rates of the transitions $i \rightarrow j$, k_{3011} , k_{1130} , k_{1120} are the cross relaxation coefficients and N_i is ion concentration. Populations N_2 and N_4 are neglected in (1)–(4) (i.e. assumed $N_2 = N_4 = 0$) because of very short non-radiative lifetimes τ_2^{nr} , τ_4^{nr} of the levels ${}^3\text{H}_5$ and ${}^3\text{F}_{2,3}$ [30]. The time derivatives in the rate equations equal zero under steady state conditions resulting in a set of nonlinear equations for populations N_i , $i = 0, \dots, 5$. Populations and stimulated rates are assumed to be dependent only on the fiber axis coordinate z .

Stimulated rates are obtained as:

$$W_{ij}(z) = \int \lambda / (hcA) \Gamma(\lambda) S(z, \lambda) \sigma_{ij}(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (6)$$

where total power spectral density is $S = S^+ + S^-$ and S^\pm [W/nm] are densities of forward (+) and backward (-) propagating fields, σ_{ij} [m^2] is the cross section of the transition $i \rightarrow j$, A [m^2] is a fiber core area, Γ [-] is the EM field overlap factor, h is the Planck constant and c is the speed of light.

Propagation of power spectral density S^\pm , which is dependent on wavelength λ [m] and position along the z , axis is modeled by the propagation equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS^\pm(z, \lambda)}{dz} = & \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} \left[\pm S^\pm(z, \lambda) [\Gamma(\lambda) (\sigma_{ij}(\lambda) N_i(z) \right. \\ & \left. - \sigma_{ji}(\lambda) N_j(z)) - \alpha(\lambda)] \right. \\ & \left. \pm 2hc^2 \lambda^{-3} \sigma_{ij}(\lambda) \Gamma(\lambda) N_i(z) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where σ_{ji} and σ_{ij} are absorption and emission cross sections of Tm^{3+} ions related to the stimulated transition between energy levels j and i , (see numbering in brackets in Fig. 1), α [m^{-1}] is intrinsic attenuation. The last term of (7) denotes the spontaneous emission power density generated in a dz segment of the fiber. The overlap Γ factor is calculated as [31,32]:

$$\Gamma = \frac{\int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\infty N(r) |E(r, \varphi)|^2 r dr d\varphi}{N_i \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\infty |E(r, \varphi)|^2 r dr d\varphi} \quad (8)$$

where $E(r, \varphi)$ is the transversal electric field profile of the mode (e.g. LP_{01}), $N(r)$ [m^{-3}] is the radial profile of the Tm^{3+} concentration and N_i is its maximum.

Finally, for laser operation at a signal wavelength λ_s , the boundary conditions at $z = 0$ and at $z = L$ (fiber end) determined using mirror reflectivities R_1, R_2 are: $S^+(0, \lambda_s) = R_1 S^-(0, \lambda_s)$ and $S^-(L, \lambda_s) = R_2 S^+(L, \lambda_s)$.

2.2. Temperature modeling

The operation of high-power fiber lasers is adversely affected by a self-heating process when the heat that is generated in the doped area of the fiber serves as a source of increased temperature of the fiber. Heat load Q_l [Wm^{-1}] is the power dissipated (transferred into heat) in a unit distance along the fiber resulting from the fact that only some part of the absorbed pump power is transferred into signal (and noise) radiation. Heat is generated mainly by non-radiative relaxation processes and at position z it is given by:

$$Q_l(z) = -\frac{dP_p^+}{dz} + \frac{dP_p^-}{dz} - \frac{dP_s^+}{dz} + \frac{dP_s^-}{dz} - \frac{dP_{\text{ASE}}^+}{dz} + \frac{dP_{\text{ASE}}^-}{dz} \quad (9)$$

where forward (+) and backward (-) pump and signal powers P_p, P_s are obtained from spectral densities S^+, S^- determined at pump and signal wavelengths λ_p, λ_s and ASE powers P_{ASE} are derived by integration of S over the whole relevant spectral range except λ_p, λ_s .

The radial profile of temperature T_c [$^\circ\text{C}$] inside the core with a radius a_1 of the circularly symmetric fiber cross section can be estimated by:

$$T_c(r) = T_b + \frac{Q a_1^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2k_1} + \sum_{i=2}^N \frac{1}{k_i} \ln \frac{a_i}{a_{i-1}} \right) - \frac{Q r^2}{4k_1} \quad (10)$$

where r [μm] is the radial distance ($r < a_1$), Q [Wm^{-3}] is the heat density in the core, T_b [$^\circ\text{C}$] is the background temperature, a_i [μm] is the outer radius of the i th layer, k_i [$\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$] is the thermal conductivity of the i th layer. Heat density is related to heat load Q_l in the core as $Q = Q_l/(\pi a_1^2)$. The formula (10) is the specialized variant (for N layers) of a more general analytical model for temperature distribution in multi-layered optical fibers with cylindrical symmetry [33]. The model assumes that the background temperature T_b is forced by a cooling medium at the outermost radius of the structure.

An example of radial distribution of temperature in the fiber cross section is shown in Fig. 2 where a fiber is heated by power absorbed in the area of a doped core with a radius $a_1 = 12.5 \mu\text{m}$. Further model layers are: silica cladding $a_2 = 200 \mu\text{m}$, polymer coating $a_3 = 250 \mu\text{m}$, thermally conducting paste $a_4 = 500 \mu\text{m}$, aluminum heat sink $a_5 = 501 \mu\text{m}$. Thermal conductivity values are $k_1 = k_2 = 1.38$, $k_3 = 0.18$, $k_4 = 5$, $k_5 = 238 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$.

The temperature is proportional to heat load and is approximately constant in the core area provided the core radius is much smaller than the cladding radius. The core temperature is generally higher in cases when layers with low thermal conductivity are present in the fiber cross section, as is seen in Fig. 2, where temperature increases sharply across the polymer coating layer. To avoid thermal damage of the standard acrylate coating its temperature must be kept below $85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (or below $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for fluoroacrylate [34]) which corresponds to a core temperature below $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the analyzed fiber (see $Q_l = 2$ and 3 W/cm curves in Fig. 2). The core temperature depends also on the position along the active fiber because heat load is a function of z according to (9).

The spectroscopic properties of thulium doped silica are known to be dependent on temperature [24]. Fig. 3 shows the spectra of emission and absorption cross sections σ_e, σ_a associated with the stimulated transitions ${}^3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow {}^3\text{H}_4$ (790 nm) and ${}^3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow {}^3\text{F}_4$ (1650, 1850 nm). The cross section spectra were derived from measurement of power loss spectra and of fluorescence emission spectra and were fitted by a function:

$$\sigma(\lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i \exp\left(-2 \left(\frac{\lambda - \lambda_i}{\delta_i}\right)^2\right) \quad (11)$$

Fig. 2. Simulation of radial distribution of temperature in a thulium-doped fiber with 25/400- μm diameter core/cladding (polymer coating thickness 50 μm , thermal paste layer thickness 250 μm). The core temperature of nearly 200 $^\circ\text{C}$ can be estimated in this scenario with 1.6 kW input single-end pump power.

Fig. 3. Absorption (solid lines) and emission (dashed lines) cross section spectra of thulium in silica at different temperatures.

where $N \geq 4$ is a number of fitting Gaussian functions and a_i, λ_i, δ_i are the parameters dependent on temperature [24]. Emission cross section spectra σ_{10} are obtained from [25]. The cross section value at a fixed wavelength is increasing or decreasing with temperature in different spectral intervals. For example, the absorption cross section σ_a of the ${}^3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow {}^3\text{F}_4$ transition decreases with temperature T for wavelengths lower than 1750 nm but increases with T for higher wavelengths.

2.3. Numerical solution

The temperature independent TDFL model described in Section 2.1 is usually solved by standard numerical methods such as Runge–Kutta integration of the system (7) (where the relevant wavelength range is discretized) combined with the numerical solution of (1)–(4) where time derivatives are set to zero to obtain a steady-state solution. To include the self-heating effect described in Section 2.2 the computation procedure is generalized by assuming the temperature dependent cross sections $\sigma_{ij}(\lambda, T)$ in (6) and (7) as follows:

1. An initial core temperature is set to a predefined value, e.g. to the background temperature T_b .
2. Based on the power distribution obtained from a previous single iteration of propagation, the heat load $Q_l(z)$ is determined from (9), core temperature $T_c(z)$ from (10) and cross sections $\sigma_{ij}(\lambda, T_c(z))$ from (11).

3. Forward and backward propagating power densities $S^\pm(z, \lambda_i)$ are solved by a numerical integration of (7) applied in forward and backward directions along the fiber using cross sections $\sigma_{ij}(\lambda, T_c(z))$ substituted into (7).
4. If convergence criteria are not met, one follows to point 2.

2.4. Analytical model

The influence of temperature on laser operation is also studied using analytical formulas derived from the analytical model of TDFLs that includes the so-called two-for-one process, essential for achieving higher efficiency of TDFLs pumped at 790 nm [35]. The formulas for slope efficiency SE [-] and threshold power P_{th} [W] are:

$$P_{th} = \frac{hcn_d}{q\lambda_p(e^{-(\alpha_p L + n_d/n_{ps})} - 1)} \quad (12)$$

$$SE = \frac{q\lambda_p}{\lambda_s} \frac{R_1(1 - R_2)(1 - e^{-(\alpha_p L + n_d/n_{ps})})}{(1 - \sqrt{R_1 R_2})(\sqrt{R_1 R_2} + R_1)} \quad (13)$$

where the total oriented flux difference n_d is:

$$n_d = n_{ss}((\ln R_1 R_2)/2 - \alpha_s L) \quad (14)$$

pump and signal absorption coefficients α_p, α_s and pump and signal saturation photon fluxes n_{ps}, n_{ss} are given by:

$$\alpha_p = \sigma_{pa} N_t \Gamma_p, \quad n_{ps} = \frac{A}{\Gamma_p \tau_1 (\sigma_{pe} + \sigma_{pa})} \quad (15)$$

$$\alpha_s = \sigma_{sa} N_t \Gamma_s, \quad n_{ss} = \frac{A}{\Gamma_s \tau_1 (\sigma_{se} + \sigma_{sa})} \quad (16)$$

and the coefficient of cross relaxation efficiency q is:

$$q = 1 + \chi_{cr}, \quad \chi_{cr} = \frac{k_{3011} N_0}{k_{3011} N_0 + 1/\tau_3}, \quad N_0 \approx N_t \quad (17)$$

In (15) and (16), $\sigma_{pa} = \sigma_{03}(\lambda_p)$, $\sigma_{sa} = \sigma_{01}(\lambda_s)$ and $\sigma_{pe} = \sigma_{30}(\lambda_p)$, $\sigma_{se} = \sigma_{10}(\lambda_s)$ denote absorption and emission cross sections at pump and signal wavelengths, Γ_p, Γ_s are pump and signal overlap factors and other quantities have been defined before. The analytical model does not include ASE. Note that the model [35] may include modeling of background (intrinsic) losses similarly to the model of Buckthorpe and Clarkson [36] but in this paper, the background losses are neglected.

3. Simulation results

Self-heating effects due to temperature dependent spectroscopic properties are demonstrated in both amplifier and laser scenarios.

3.1. Amplifier

Before the general numerical model is applied it is instructive to analyze amplifier gain using a known analytical formula [32]. A gain coefficient, G [-], of a fiber amplifier with a two-level system is defined by a relation between input and output signal powers: $P_s(L) = P_s(0) \exp(G)$ and is determined as:

$$G = \Gamma_s \left((\sigma_{se} + \sigma_{sa}) \overline{N_1} - \sigma_{sa} N_t \right) L \quad (18)$$

where $\overline{N_1}$ is the average value of population N_1 along the active fiber of length L . Fig. 4 shows the gain coefficient spectral characteristics determined by (18) for different temperatures with constant N_1 population ($N_1/N_t = 2\%, 5\%$). Temperature dependent cross sections are obtained from (11). Gain coefficient characteristics are shifted towards longer signal wavelengths with increasing temperature. Remarkably, there is a transparency wavelength λ_t where the gain coefficient is zero and so from (18) the condition:

$$\frac{\sigma_{se}(\lambda_t)}{\sigma_{sa}(\lambda_t)} = \frac{N_t - \overline{N_1}}{\overline{N_1}} \quad (19)$$

Fig. 4. Gain coefficient spectra for several core temperatures, relative population of metastable level is 5% (solid lines) and 2% (dashed lines).

is fulfilled. Since the value λ_t is sensitive to temperature, it is expected that the greatest influence of temperature would be observed at signal wavelengths in the vicinity of the transparency wavelength.

The amplifier simulation using a comprehensive numerical model with parameters summarized in Table 1 (thulium concentration 6.06 wt%, lifetimes and cross relaxation coefficients according to [37], other unspecified parameters according to [27]) was carried out to demonstrate the self-heating effect. Cladding pumping is assumed in models of both amplifier and laser. This corresponds to small values of pump overlap factor Γ_p in Table 1. Cladding pumping is realized by means of double-clad fibers where the inner cladding and doped core together guide the pump light. Therefore the results presented are relevant for double-clad doped fibers.

Core and cladding diameters of the model are chosen with practical application in mind since the active fibers with core/cladding diameter of 20/400 (or 25/400) μm are considered as standard for high-power fiber laser/amplifier applications [38]. On the other hand, small diameter commercial fibers 8/125 μm are more appropriate for medium power (\sim tens of Watts) and are not optimal for high-power lasers. A larger core leads to a large mode area that is beneficial for decreasing nonlinear effects [8]. Also, larger cladding assures lower temperature of (standard) coating with the same heat load, see e.g. Fig. 3 in [33]. Nevertheless, general conclusions obtained from simulations presented below are valid even for active fibers with different core/cladding diameters.

Fig. 5 compares simulated distributions of power and core temperature along the thulium-doped fiber amplifier (TDFA) working at a signal wavelength 1907 nm, assuming self-heating (solid lines) and assuming fixed room temperature only (dashed lines). At the beginning of the active fiber, the core temperature reaches 143 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, which corresponds to the heat load 1.65 W/cm, and decreases along the fiber towards the background temperature $T_b = 40$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$. When the self-heating effect and temperature dependent thulium cross sections are taken into account, the pump power is absorbed slightly slower than in the case of a fixed core temperature 23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, but there is a dramatic change in signal power distribution along the fiber. While the signal power increases monotonically in the simulation with a fixed low temperature, the self-heating simulation leads to the signal power being larger than the ASE power only in the interval from 1.3 m to 7.4 m and greatly reduced at the fiber end. The signal power is diminished at both fiber ends at the expense of a significant rise of the ASE power — the backward propagating ASE power reaches 414 W at the fiber beginning, the forward propagating ASE power reaches 579 W at the fiber end.

Fig. 6 shows the spatial distribution of power spectra around 2 μm and two cases are compared. Figs. 6a, b show how, when the self-heating is modeled, the forward and backward ASE power spectra are

Table 1
Simulation parameters for thulium-doped fiber amplifier.

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Value
Fiber length	L	m	8
Fiber core diameter	d_c	μm	20
Fiber cladding diam.	d_{cl}	μm	400
Total thulium conc.	N_t	m^{-3}	4.7×10^{26}
Overlap at signal	Γ_s	-	0.9
Overlap at pump	Γ_p	-	0.0015
Pump power	P_p	W	1600
Signal wavelength	λ_s	nm	1907
Pump wavelength	λ_p	nm	790
Intrinsic attenuation	α	dB/m	0.012
$^3\text{F}_4$ lifetime	τ_1	μs	585
$^3\text{H}_4$ lifetime	τ_3	μs	51
$^1\text{G}_4$ lifetime	τ_5	μs	784
Cross relaxation coef.	k_{3011}	m^3/s	1.9×10^{-22}
Cross relaxation coef.	k_{1130}	m^3/s	1.4×10^{-23}
Cross relaxation coef.	k_{1120}	m^3/s	3.5×10^{-23}

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution of optical powers, core temperature and heat load on a TDFA at a signal wavelength of 1907 nm. Self-heating effect (solid lines) vs fixed room temperature $T = 23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (dashed lines).

strongly amplified along the fiber such that the absorbed pumping power is transferred into wide-band noise-like spectral components centered at around $2 \mu\text{m}$. This is in contrast with the analogous simulation in Figs. 6c, d with the core temperature fixed at room temperature ($23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), where the ASE power is weakly amplified along the fiber and remains small compared to the signal power at 1907 nm.

Note that fully resolved ASE spectra involving the whole emission spectral range (1500–2200 nm) are needed to simulate this thermal effect properly. It was checked that the drop of output signal is not modeled correctly when the amplifier is simulated without ASE or when ASE is approximated using the effective ASE bandwidth as described in [20,29].

The wavelength dependence of the signal and forward ASE output powers is shown in Fig. 7. Two fiber lengths ($L = 6 \text{ m}$ and 8 m) are analyzed and the self-heating effect is compared with the case of fixed low core temperature (dashed lines). At long wavelengths, the signal power reaches its maximum and the ASE power is negligible. With decreasing wavelength, the ASE power increases and signal power decreases until they become comparable. For even shorter wavelengths, the output ASE eventually dominates in power over the output signal which becomes diminished. As seen in Fig. 7, the maximum forward ASE is about half of the maximum signal since the backward propagating ASE carries approximately the same amount of power too. The self-heating process causes the drop of signal power to occur at longer wavelengths than expected from a low temperature prediction. In the analyzed case, the shift is about 15 nm for fiber length $L = 7 \text{ m}$, (see blue solid and dashed lines in Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Spatial evolution of power spectra on TDFA. (a) forward propagating field in self-heated fiber, (b) backward propagating field in self-heated fiber, (c) forward propagating field in fiber with fixed core temperature $T_c = 23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, (d) backward propagating field, $T_c = 23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 7. Output signal power (P_{sout}) of TDFA and output forward ASE power dependence on signal wavelength for two fiber lengths L . Self-heating effect (solid lines) vs fixed room temperature $T = 23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (dashed lines).

The pump power used in Figs. 5, 6 and 7 is 1600 W as stated in Table 1. Increasing the pump power beyond 1600 W will not lead to a proportional increase of signal output power as most of the pump power will get converted into ASE and heat. However with pump power significantly larger than 1600 W, the simulated fiber can exceed thermal damage temperature of coating as discussed in Section 2.2 and demonstrated in Fig. 2.

3.2. Laser

A laser in a Fabry–Perot configuration is considered with the following parameters: the reflectivities $R_1 = 0.99$, $R_2 = 0.036$, the core diameter $d_c = 25 \mu\text{m}$ and the pump overlap $\Gamma_p = 0.0024$. Other parameters are in Table 1 or stated below.

The temperature effects on laser operation are studied first using the analytical formulas (12), (13). Fig. 8 shows the slope efficiency and threshold power as a function of fiber length for different core temperatures. The threshold power reaches a minimum for a certain value of L but then increases steadily. The slope efficiency increases with L until it saturates at a constant value for large values of L . High core temperature causes the threshold power to increase significantly regardless of L . The slope efficiency decreases with temperature but

Fig. 8. Threshold power and slope efficiency of TDFL for different temperatures. Fiber length dependence for signal wavelength $\lambda_s = 1938$ nm.

Fig. 9. Threshold power and slope efficiency of TDFL for different temperatures. Signal wavelength dependence for fiber length $L = 3.41$ m.

this effect is most prominent only for fiber lengths below 4 meters where the laser does not operate with its optimal efficiency. The SE values computed with the numerical model, shown in Fig. 8 by green lines, are nearly equal to those from the analytical model.

Fig. 9 shows the slope efficiency and threshold power as a function of the signal wavelength for different core temperatures and for a fiber length $L = 3.41$ m. Such a length was determined as $L = L_{13\text{dB}} \equiv 13 / (10 \log(e) \Gamma_p \sigma_{pa} N_f)$ at room temperature and represents the practical estimation of the fiber length where the pump absorption reaches 13 dB, i.e., at this fiber length 95% of pump light is absorbed. The threshold power exhibits a minimum at a specific wavelength and this is increasing and shifting towards higher wavelengths with increasing core temperature. The analytical model provides the slope efficiency values remaining almost constant in the wavelength range 1900–2000 nm except at higher temperatures. The full numerical model including ASE gives the SE values slightly decreasing (see green lines). The SE values at the wavelengths where the threshold increases very steeply are not relevant. That is also why the SE values from the numerical model are shown only in the range 1900–2000 nm. Furthermore, similarly as in the case of the amplifier, the correct modeling of temperature effects in the range, where ASE is expected to be significant, requires the full spectrally resolved ASE model where the spectral evolution of the ASE is evaluated using Eq. (7).

Slope efficiency values determined using the analytical and numerical models for different temperatures are listed in Table 2. The relative change of SE due to an increased core temperature is expressed in the

Table 2

Slope efficiency vs core temperature from analytical (SE_a) and numerical (SE_n) models of TDFL for $\lambda_s = 1938$ nm, $L = 3.41$ m.

T_c [°C]	SE_a [-]	SE_n [-]	ΔSE_a [%]	ΔSE_n [%]
23	0.730	0.703	0	0
100	0.722	0.692	-1.10	-1.51
200	0.701	0.672	-3.97	-4.25

Fig. 10. Spatial distribution of optical powers, core temperature and heat load on a TDFL at a signal wavelength of 1900 nm. Self-heating effect (solid lines) vs fixed room temperature $T = 23$ °C (dashed lines).

last two columns as $\Delta SE = (SE_{T_c} - SE_{23^\circ\text{C}}) / SE_{23^\circ\text{C}}$. SE dropped by more than 4% as predicted by both analytical and numerical models assuming a constant temperature 200 °C along the fiber, which can be understood as the worst case scenario since in reality, the distribution of temperature is not constant along the fiber.

While the analytical model offers advantages of quick physical insight and easy implementation, a more realistic laser simulation using a comprehensive numerical model was carried out to demonstrate the self-heating effect.

Fig. 10 compares simulated distributions of power and core temperature along the TDFL working at a signal wavelength 1900 nm, assuming self-heating (solid lines) and assuming fixed room temperature only (dashed lines). Background temperature is $T_b = 40$ °C. At the beginning of the active fiber, the heat load in the core exceeds 2.3 W/cm, the core temperature reaches 175 °C and decreases along the fiber. Self-heating causes significant drop of a signal power and the rise of ASE.

Fig. 11 shows the output laser characteristics with and without self-heating modeling. The output signal power P_{sout} increases linearly with the pump power P_p when the active fiber is simulated without self-heating. On the other hand, when self-heating is modeled by the procedure described in Section 2.3 and estimating the background temperature using $T_b = 23 + 17(P_p/1600)$ °C, the output power increases linearly only for low pump powers, however when P_p is greater than 1 kW, the rate dP_s/dP_p is gradually reduced until P_{sout} reaches its maximum for a certain value P_p . When P_p is further increased, the output power declines rapidly. At the same time, the forward ASE rises with pump power until, similarly as in the amplifier case, becomes dominant over signal, (see dashed lines in Fig. 11). The effect is strongly dependent on signal wavelength in the vicinity of the transparency wavelength defined in Section 3.1 (as illustrated in Fig. 11) since the maximum of P_{sout} is much larger at 1905 nm. For even longer wavelengths, the output power is not reduced due to self-heating.

Fig. 12 shows the dependence of the output power on the fiber length L for a fiber with a fixed core temperature and for a self-heated fiber. The output signal power increases with the fiber length and gradually saturates at a constant maximum value when the active

Fig. 11. Output laser characteristics for fiber length $L = 6$ m and different signal wavelengths; output signal power P_{sout} (solid lines) vs output forward ASE (dashed lines).

Fig. 12. Output power as a function of fiber length for pump power $P_p = 1600$ W and different signal wavelengths; output signal power P_{sout} (solid lines) vs output forward ASE (dashed lines).

fiber is simulated without self-heating. On the other hand, when self-heating is modeled, the output power increases with L , then it reaches its maximum and declines when L is further increased. When fiber length is increasing, the output signal drops eventually due to ASE, (see the black curve for fixed core temperature in Fig. 12). The self-heating causes ASE to become more prominent and dominantly impair wavelengths near the transparency wavelength. The adverse effect of self-heating can be mitigated to some extent by choosing a fiber length that is shorter than optimal.

4. Conclusion

The temperature related effects in thulium-doped active fibers that are a direct consequence of temperature dependence of spectroscopic parameters of the Tm^{3+} ions in silica were studied by means of simulations, using both analytical and numerical models.

The performance of TDFLs is affected by following effects: (1) Slope efficiency (SE) is decreased due to temperature change of absorption and emission cross sections as demonstrated in Fig. 8. The drop of SE is relatively small, see Table 2, but clearly notable. (2) Enhanced ASE power for signal wavelengths near the transparency wavelength can cause a significant drop or complete loss of output signal power that is not expected to happen when temperature dependent cross sections are not taken into account.

Considering enhanced ASE, it was revealed that gain coefficient spectra shift with increasing temperature towards higher wavelengths, which has important consequences for high-power thulium-doped amplifiers or lasers operating at signal wavelengths near the transparency wavelength. Once the spontaneous emission is amplified with a gain comparable to or larger than the signal gain, the power in forward and backward propagating ASE could eventually, for sufficiently long fibers, consume the vast majority of energy stored in the laser resonator, leaving the signal attenuated or completely diminished at the laser output.

While the self-heating process leads to a more elevated ASE power compared to signal power, the exact ratio of the two at a given wavelength depends on exact relations between absorption and emission temperature dependent spectra of thulium cross sections associated with the transition 3F_4 - 3H_6 around 1900 nm. Therefore different spectral models (11), obtained e.g. from different measurements, can give the different transparency wavelengths and self-heating effects predicted at different signal wavelengths.

As pointed out previously, the adverse effect of elevated ASE due to self-heating can be mitigated to some extent by choosing a shorter active fiber. A fiber that is shorter than optimal will provide a lower output power, as was also demonstrated by our simulations. For typical lengths of double-clad active fiber, where 95% of the pump is absorbed, so-called 13-dB fiber length, the decrease of up 4% of the laser slope efficiency at 1938 nm laser wavelength was predicted by the analytical model. Other more sophisticated means for ASE suppression such as using a photonic crystal fiber [4] or depressed cladding [39,40], were proved to permit a TDFA operation even below 1800 nm. Nevertheless, even with these techniques, the temperature induced effects due to self-heating should always be taken into account when high-power TDFLs/TDFAs are designed.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Martin Grábner: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Bára Švejkarová:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Jan Aubrecht:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology. **Jan Pokorný:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Pavel Honzátko:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Pavel Peterka:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Czech Science Foundation, project No. 23-05701S and co-funded by European Union and the state budget of the Czech republic under the project LasApp CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004573.

The authors thank Martin Buckthorpe from University of Southampton for careful proof reading of this paper.

References

- [1] F. Todorov, J. Aubrecht, P. Peterka, O. Schreiber, A.A. Jasim, J. Mrázek, O. Podrázky, M. Kamrádek, N. Kanagaraj, M. Grábner, et al., Active optical fibers and components for fiber lasers emitting in the 2- μm spectral range, *Materials* 13 (22) (2020) 5177.
- [2] C. Jollivet, K. Farley, M. Conroy, H. Dabhi, J. Edgecumbe, A. Carter, K. Tankala, Design optimization of Tm-doped large-mode area fibers for power scaling of 2 μm lasers and amplifiers, in: *Fiber Lasers XIV: Technology and Systems*, vol. 10083, SPIE, 2017, pp. 89–95.
- [3] M. Michalska, P. Honzátko, P. Grzes, M. Kamrádek, O. Podrázky, I. Kasik, J. Swiderski, Thulium-doped 1940- and 2034-nm fiber amplifiers: Towards highly efficient, high-power all-fiber laser systems, *J. Lightwave Technol.* 42 (1) (2024) 339–346, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/JLT.2023.3301397>.
- [4] S.D. Emami, M.M. Dashtabi, H.J. Lee, A.S. Arabanian, H.A.A. Rashid, 1700 nm and 1800 nm band tunable thulium doped mode-locked fiber lasers, *Sci. Rep.* 7 (1) (2017) 12747.
- [5] J. Aubrecht, J. Pokorný, M. Kamrádek, B. Jiříčková, P. Peterka, Design and characterization of thulium-doped fiber with depressed cladding for amplifiers operating in the region from L-band to 1.8 μm , in: 2023 Conference on Lasers and Electro-Optics Europe & European Quantum Electronics Conference, CLEO/Europe-EQEC, IEEE, 2023, p. 1.
- [6] J. Li, Z. Sun, H. Luo, Z. Yan, K. Zhou, Y. Liu, L. Zhang, Wide wavelength selectable all-fiber thulium doped fiber laser between 1925 nm and 2200 nm, *Opt. Express* 22 (5) (2014) 5387–5399.
- [7] C. Jauregui, J. Limpert, A. Tünnermann, High-power fibre lasers, *Nature Photonics* 7 (11) (2013) 861–867.
- [8] M.N. Zervas, C.A. Codemard, High power fiber lasers: A review, *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Quantum Electron.* 20 (5) (2014) 219–241, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/JSTQE.2014.2321279>.
- [9] J.W. Dawson, M.J. Messerly, R.J. Beach, M.Y. Shverdin, E.A. Stappaerts, A.K. Sridharan, P.H. Pax, J.E. Heebner, C.W. Siders, C. Barty, Analysis of the scalability of diffraction-limited fiber lasers and amplifiers to high average power, *Optics Express* 16 (17) (2008) 13240–13266.
- [10] M.-A. Lapointe, S. Chatigny, M. Piché, M. Cain-Skaff, J.-N. Maran, Thermal effects in high-power CW fiber lasers, in: *Fiber Lasers VI: Technology, Systems, and Applications*, vol. 7195, SPIE, 2009, pp. 430–440.
- [11] C. Jauregui, C. Stihler, J. Limpert, Transverse mode instability, *Adv. Optics Photonics* 12 (2) (2020) 429–484.
- [12] L. Zenteno, High-power double-clad fiber lasers, *J. Lightwave Technol.* 11 (9) (1993) 1435–1446.
- [13] Y. Wang, Heat dissipation in kilowatt fiber power amplifiers, *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* 40 (6) (2004) 731–740.
- [14] M. Karimi, Theoretical study of the thermal distribution in yb-doped double-clad fiber laser by considering different heat sources, *Prog. Electromagn. Res. C* 88 (2018) 59–76.
- [15] C. Jauregui, T. Eidam, J. Limpert, A. Tünnermann, Impact of modal interference on the beam quality of high-power fiber amplifiers, *Optics Express* 19 (4) (2011) 3258–3271.
- [16] A.V. Smith, J.J. Smith, Mode instability in high power fiber amplifiers, *Optics Express* 19 (11) (2011) 10180–10192.
- [17] K.R. Hansen, T.T. Alkeskjold, J. Broeng, J. Lægsgaard, Theoretical analysis of mode instability in high-power fiber amplifiers, *Optics Express* 21 (2) (2013) 1944–1971.
- [18] A.V. Smith, J.J. Smith, Mode instability thresholds for Tm-doped fiber amplifiers pumped at 790 nm, *Opt. Express* 24 (2) (2016) 975–992, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1364/OE.24.000975>.
- [19] C. Gaida, M. Gebhardt, T. Heuermann, Z. Wang, C. Jauregui, J. Limpert, Transverse mode instability and thermal effects in thulium-doped fiber amplifiers under high thermal loads, *Opt. Express* 29 (10) (2021) 14963–14973.
- [20] C. Huang, Y. Tang, H. Li, Y. Wang, J. Xu, C. Du, A versatile model for temperature-dependent effects in Tm-doped silica fiber lasers, *J. Lightwave Technol.* 32 (3) (2014) 421–428.
- [21] M. Bolshtyansky, P. Wysocki, N. Conti, Model of temperature dependence for gain shape of erbium-doped fiber amplifier, *J. Lightwave Technol.* 18 (11) (2000) 1533.
- [22] M. Tao, J. Ye, X. Ye, G. Feng, Y. Wang, T. Yu, Y. Qi, Z. Quan, W. Chen, Thermal modeling of resonantly pumped high power Tm-doped fiber amplifiers, *Results Phys.* 36 (2022) 105407.
- [23] D. Panitzek, C. Romano, M. Eichhorn, C. Kieleck, Temperature investigation of low SWaP thulium-doped fiber lasers, *Opt. Express* 32 (2) (2024) 1890–1901.
- [24] B. Jiříčková, M. Grábner, C. Jauregui, J. Aubrecht, O. Schreiber, P. Peterka, Temperature-dependent cross section spectra for thulium-doped fiber lasers, *Opt. Lett.* 48 (3) (2023) 811–814.
- [25] B. Jiříčková, R. Švejkar, M. Grábner, C. Jauregui, J. Aubrecht, O. Schreiber, P. Peterka, Temperature-dependent emission cross-section spectra at 1.8 μm of the thulium-doped fibers cooled down to cryogenic temperatures, in: *The European Conference on Lasers and Electro-Optics*, Optica Publishing Group, 2023, cj_10_6.
- [26] S. Jackson, T. King, Theoretical modeling of Tm-doped silica fiber lasers, *J. Lightwave Technol.* 17 (5) (1999) 948–956, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/50.762916>.
- [27] P. Peterka, B. Faure, W. Blanc, M. Karasek, B. Dussardier, Theoretical modelling of S-band thulium-doped silica fibre amplifiers, *Opt. Quantum Electron.* 36 (1) (2004) 201–212.
- [28] M. Eichhorn, Numerical modeling of Tm-doped double-clad fluoride fiber amplifiers, *IEEE J. Quantum Electron.* 41 (12) (2005) 1574–1581.
- [29] M.A. Khamis, K. Ennser, Theoretical model of a thulium-doped fiber amplifier pumped at 1570 nm and 793 nm in the presence of cross relaxation, *J. Lightwave Technol.* 34 (24) (2016) 5675–5681.
- [30] J. Yang, Y. Wang, Y. Tang, J. Xu, Influences of pump transitions on thermal effects of multi-kilowatt thulium-doped fiber lasers, 2015, arXiv preprint arXiv: 1503.07256.
- [31] P.M. Becker, A.A. Olsson, J.R. Simpson, *Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifiers: Fundamentals and Technology*, Elsevier, 1999.
- [32] E. Desurvire, *Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifiers: Principles and Applications*, Wiley, 1994.
- [33] M. Grábner, P. Peterka, P. Honzátko, Formula for temperature distribution in multi-layer optical fibres for high-power fiber lasers, *Opto-Electron. Rev.* 29 (4) (2021) <http://dx.doi.org/10.24425/opelre.2021.139482>.
- [34] G.D. Goodno, L.D. Book, J.E. Rothenberg, M.E. Weber, S. Benjamin Weiss, Narrow linewidth power scaling and phase stabilization of 2- μm thulium fiber lasers, *Opt. Eng.*, Bellingham 50 (11) (2011) 111608.
- [35] M. Grábner, B. Švejkarová, J. Aubrecht, P. Peterka, Analytical model of thulium-doped fiber laser pumped by two-for-one process, *J. Lightwave Technol.* 42 (8) (2024) 2938–2944, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/JLT.2023.3345001>.
- [36] M.P. Buckthorpe, W.A. Clarkson, Simple method for determining quantum efficiency and background propagation loss in thulium-doped fibres, *Appl. Phys. B* 129 (9) (2023) 142, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00340-023-08084-x>.
- [37] M. Kamrádek, J. Aubrecht, P. Vařák, J. Cajzl, V. Kubeček, P. Honzátko, I. Kašík, P. Peterka, Energy transfer coefficients in thulium-doped silica fibers, *Opt. Mater. Express* 11 (6) (2021) 1805–1814.
- [38] J. Zuo, X. Lin, High-power laser systems, *Laser Photonics Rev.* 16 (5) (2022) 2100741.
- [39] J. Aubrecht, J. Pokorný, B. Švejkarová, M. Kamrádek, P. Peterka, Broadband thulium fiber amplifier for spectral region located beyond the L-band, *Opt. Express* 32 (10) (2024) 17932–17941, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1364/OE.522088>.
- [40] J. Pokorný, J. Aubrecht, M. Kamrádek, B. Švejkarová, P. Vařák, M. Grábner, P. Peterka, Depressed-cladding thulium-doped fiber for applications below 1800 nm, *Opt. Express* 32 (10) (2024) 17966–17976, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1364/OE.523168>.